

Constraints on Convection and Overshoot

Catherine Lovekin¹

¹ Department of Physics, Mount Allison University, Canada

Abstract

Convection is one of the major mixing processes in stars, and is crucial for understanding their structure and evolution. One area of uncertainty is the amount of convective mixing that extends beyond the convective boundary, described by the convective overshoot parameter. This extra mixing effectively extends the convective region, changing the properties of the star. However, these processes occur in the deep interior of the star, and cannot be observed directly. For this reason, the extent of the overshoot region is highly uncertain, and whether and how it changes with the stellar properties is unknown. The overshoot parameter can be determined using its effects on the pulsation frequencies of a star, but the detailed modelling required has only been done for a few stars. In this talk, I will summarize how we determine convective overshoot in stars, and what this tells us about the behaviour of the convective overshoot parameter.

1 Introduction

Convection is an important process in stellar interiors, responsible for energy transport, but also mixing of chemically enriched material in the core. Normally, the extent of a convective region is determined by the Schwarzschild criterion (Schwarzschild, 1958), which produces a convective region with a sharp boundary. However, more detailed simulations indicate the presence of convective overshoot, an extension of the mixing beyond the theoretical convective boundary. In stars with convective cores, this extra mixing effectively enlarges the convective core, extending the main sequence lifetime of the star (see, for example, Eggenberger *et al.*, 2010). In the past, the convective overshooting has been parameterized using a step overshooting model, where the convective region is extended by some fraction of a pressure scale height H_P beyond the theoretical boundary:

$$D = \alpha_{ov} H_P \quad (1)$$

where α_{ov} is the convective overshoot parameter. This parameter is taken to be a constant as the star evolves, and typical values range from $\alpha_{ov} = 0.1 - 0.3$ to match observations of the width of the main sequence and models of binary star systems. In general, the parameter is chosen to be independent of the mass of the star, although some model grids have used a mass-dependent parameter (Demarque *et al.*, 2004). Measurements have been made using eclipsing binaries with well constrained masses and radii suggesting there is some mass dependence, at least below $\sim 2 M_\odot$ (Claret & Torres, 2016) but the sample sizes remain small.

At present, it is not entirely clear whether the overshoot parameter should vary with the mass and age of the star. There is also uncertainty in how the shape of the overshoot region should be modelled. Conventional step overshoot approaches using α_{ov} treat the overshoot region as an extension of the convective core, and material is mixed as uniformly and efficiently in the overshoot region as in the core itself. However, numerical simulations suggest this may not be a realistic model for the behaviour of the convective overshoot. An alternative model treats the convective overshoot as a diffusion coefficient,

$$D_{ov} = D_o \exp\left(\frac{2z}{f_{ov} H_P}\right) \quad (2)$$

which exponentially decays as the distance z away from the convective boundary increases (Herwig, 2000). In this

model, the overshoot parameter f_{ov} controls how quickly the strength of the overshooting decays, and is thought to more realistically model how the convective overshooting becomes less effective with distance from the theoretical core boundary.

Asteroseismology provides a useful probe of stellar interiors across the HR diagram, but here we focus on four classes of main sequence pulsating stars with convective cores. The β Cephei stars and δ Scuti stars are both p -mode pulsators, with periods of a few hours or less. β Cephei stars are B stars, with spectral types between B0 and B2 Aussenloos *et al.* (2004). δ Scuti stars are lower mass, around $2-2.5 M_\odot$, and are located where the classical instability strip intersects the main sequence. In both classes of stars, the pulsation modes are driven by the κ mechanism in the Fe and He ionization zones respectively, and tend to probe the surface regions of the star rather than the deep interior. While β Cephei stars usually pulsate in only a few strong modes, space-based observations of δ Scuti stars have revealed rich and complex pulsation spectra. In both cases, the observed pulsation modes are generally non-radial. A subclass of δ Scuti stars, the High Amplitude Delta Scuti (HADS) stars are thought to pulsate mainly in radial modes. Although it has been suggested that the HADS are more evolved objects, intermediate between normal δ Scuti stars and the classical Cepheids, the two types appear to be drawn from the same population (Balona, 2016). HADS are relatively rare, and account for a small fraction of the total population of δ Scuti stars (Lee *et al.*, 2008).

Slowly Pulsating B (SPB) and γ Doradus stars both pulsate in g modes. The SPB stars are B type stars, and hybrid SPB/ β Cephei stars seem to be common. The γ Doradus stars are of particular interest, as their masses ($1.4-2.5 M_\odot$) fall in the transition range from stars with convective envelopes and radiative cores to stars with convective cores and radiative envelopes. As such, these stars often have both convective cores and convective envelopes. The g modes in the γ Doradus stars are thought to be driven by convective flux blocking at the bottom of the convective envelope (Guzik *et al.*, 2000; Dupret *et al.*, 2005), and the modes probe the interior of the star up to the top of the convective core. As a result, the g modes in γ Doradus stars are very sensitive to the convective properties of the star, so asteroseismic analysis of these stars has the potential to teach us much about convective overshoot. However, the pulsation periods in these stars are typically $0.3-3 \text{ d}^{-1}$, which combined with a lower amplitude

makes these modes very difficult to detect from the ground. Space missions such as *Kepler* (Koch *et al.*, 2010) have given us access to long time series with very high precision, resulting in the detection of many modes in these stars.

Theoretically, g modes are expected to show uniform period spacing for radial orders n of a mode of a given spherical harmonic ℓ if $n \gg \ell$, assuming no rotation and a chemically homogeneous radiative envelope (Tassoul, 1980). In more realistic models, Miglio *et al.* (2008) showed that the presence of a chemical gradient at the boundary of the convective core produces a series of periodic dips in the observed period spacings. The patterns in the period spacings are further complicated by the presence of convective overshoot and rotation. Convective overshoot reduces the size of the chemical gradient, which washes out the dips. Rotation causes mode splitting, and the period spacing pattern produced depends on the azimuthal order m . Prograde modes with $0 < m < \ell$ are expected to be easiest to detect, but stars have been detected with prograde, retrograde ($-\ell < m < 0$), and zonal ($m = 0$) modes (Van Reeth *et al.*, 2016). By careful modelling of these effects, it is possible to determine the pulsation modes, rotation rate, and core overshoot parameter of a star.

In recent years, extremely high precision asteroseismology using space missions such as MOST (Walker *et al.*, 2003), CoRoT (Auvergne *et al.*, 2009), and *Kepler* (Koch *et al.*, 2010) have provided us with rich and detailed pulsation spectra for thousands of stars. The detailed pulsation spectra produced are opening up new analysis techniques, allowing us to learn more about the behaviour of the convective overshoot. As a result of this data, many of the existing δ Scuti stars have been shown to be hybrid pulsators, with both p and g modes. These stars are particularly useful for studying the behaviour of the convective overshoot, as the combination of modes probes both the surface regions and the core.

In this review, we will discuss constraints on overshoot that can be placed on individual stars (Section 2) and on groups of stars (Section 3) using p -mode frequencies. In Section 4 we will discuss recent progress towards constraining the overshoot in g -mode pulsators. Our conclusions are summarized in Section 5.

2 β Cephei stars

One of the earliest attempts to constrain the extent of convective overshooting using asteroseismology was done for ν Eridani Ausseleos *et al.* (2004), based on a 5 month campaign of spectroscopic and photometric ground-based observations. This extensive campaign resulted in 8 well determined frequencies in the photometric data and 7 in the spectroscopic data. Of these, 4 frequencies appearing in both data sets were modelled by comparing the observed frequencies to a grid of models calculated using CLES (Code Liégeois d'Évolution Stellaire). Initially, models were selected which provided a fit for the mode identified as the radial fundamental mode, fixing the age of the model. Next, the $\ell = 1$, g_1 mode was included, which fixed the mass of the model. Adding a third frequency ($\ell = 1$, p_1) fixed the metallicity of the model, while the fourth frequency ($\ell = 1$, p_2) fixed the convective overshoot parameter, α_{ov} . As shown in Figure 1, matching all four observed frequencies required an overshoot parameter of $\alpha_{ov} > 0.3$, which they considered unreasonably high. By introducing an artificially enhanced iron abundance in the driving region, they were able to reproduce the observed frequencies with an overshoot parameter of $\alpha_{ov} = 0.21$, which is more consistent with the values found in other stars.

A similar technique was used by Aerts *et al.* (2003) to mea-

Figure 1: Fitting models to the observed frequencies for ν Eridani. In this case, models are eliminated by fitting 2 frequencies, then 3, before finally fitting all four observed frequencies. The x axis marks the value of the $\ell = 1$, p_2 mode and the y axis marks the $\ell = 1$, p_1 mode. The four sequences show overshoots of (right to left) $\alpha_{ov} = 0.0, 0.1, 0.2$, and 0.3 , while the metallicity ranges from 0.012 to 0.030 with steps of 0.002. Figure from Ausseleos *et al.* (2004).

sure the convective overshoot in HD129929 based on ground based observations. A total of six frequencies were detected, and stellar models showed that a core overshoot parameter of $\alpha_{ov} = 0.1$ was required to reproduce the observations. The results also showed that the core of the star could not be undergoing rigid rotation to be consistent with the observed frequencies.

In general, this technique for fitting observed frequencies to a grid of stellar models relies on spectroscopic mode identification. However, spectroscopic mode identification is a time consuming process, and this information is often not available for stars observed as part of a large photometric survey, or for very faint stars. In order to constrain overshoot this way, the star must be bright enough to be observed using ground-based spectroscopy, and then modelled in detail.

Attempts have been made to apply this technique using only photometric data, without constraints placed by mode identification (Neiner *et al.*, 2012; Lovekin & Goupil, 2010). In Lovekin & Goupil (2010) all 7 frequencies observed in θ Ophiuchi were fit simultaneously using 2D rotating models of fixed age, metallicity, and mass (Deupree, 1990, 1995) using a modified χ^2 statistic. The total χ^2 for a particular model was given by

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum (\nu_{the,i} - \nu_{obs,i})^2 \quad (3)$$

where N is the total number of frequencies fit for each model. This can either be done completely without constraints from mode identification, or by including the constraints and only comparing frequencies of the same ℓ . Using the mode identification results in a more accurate, better constrained fit, but Lovekin & Goupil (2010) found that it is possible to model the observed frequencies when the mode identification is unknown. With the photometric constraints, Lovekin & Goupil (2010) found the overshoot parameter for θ Ophiuchi to be $\alpha_{ov} = 0.28$, as shown in Figure 2. This value is higher than most β Cephei stars, which seem to have overshoot parameters of $\alpha_{ov} = 0.1 - 0.2$, but is in agreement with previous work done on θ Ophiuchi, which found $\alpha_{ov} = 0.44$ (Briquet

Figure 2: A χ^2 map (Equation 3) showing the best fits for rotation and convective core overshoot in θ Ophiuchi. The grid of models was held fixed at $9.5 M_{\odot}$ and all were evolved to an age of 15.6 Myr. Figure from Lovekin & Goupil (2010).

et al., 2007). In Neiner *et al.* (2012), this method was extended to allow the mass and age to be free parameters and applied to two Be stars observed with CoRoT.

Asteroseismic analysis in this manner is time consuming, both from an observational perspective and a theoretical perspective. For all of the β Cephei stars with known overshoot parameters, extensive ground-based spectroscopy has been collected. The modelling process is also time-consuming, and is not suitable for application to the large number of stars with photometric frequencies from CoRoT, *Kepler*, and the upcoming data from TESS (Ricker *et al.*, 2015). In general, assumptions are made and some of the stellar properties are held fixed to reduce the available parameter space. Nevertheless, this type of technique has been used to constrain the convective core overshoot parameter for a handful of β Cephei stars, including θ Ophiuchi ($\alpha_{ov} = 0.3-0.4$) (Briquet *et al.*, 2005; Handler *et al.*, 2005; Briquet *et al.*, 2007; Lovekin & Goupil, 2010), 12 Lacertae ($\alpha_{ov} < 0.4$) (Handler *et al.*, 2006; Desmet *et al.*, 2009), β Canis Majoris ($\alpha_{ov} = 0.2$) (Mazumdar *et al.*, 2006), and HD129929 ($\alpha_{ov} = 0.1$) (Aerts *et al.*, 2003, 2004). Although there appears to be some consistency in the convective overshoot across the β Cephei stars, the available sample is still too small to draw any meaningful conclusions.

3 Q values

Recently, (Lovekin & Guzik, 2017) investigated the behaviour of theoretical p-modes in stellar models between 1.2 and $2.2 M_{\odot}$. This mass range covers the transition between convective cores and convective envelopes, and includes both γ Doradus and δ Scuti pulsators. These models were calculated using MESA Paxton *et al.* (2011, 2013, 2015, 2018) and use the exponential overshoot prescription, with f_{ov} from 0 to 0.1. Models were evolved to the end of the main sequence, and pulsation frequencies calculated at 5 points along the main sequence using GYRE Townsend & Teitler (2013). They then calculated the pulsation constant

$$Q = \Pi \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\rho_{\odot}}} \quad (4)$$

Figure 3: The variation in the pulsation constant for the first 7 harmonics of the radial mode in non-rotating models with no convective overshoot. Each model was fit with a 4 parameter piecewise linear fit. Adapted from Lovekin & Guzik (2017).

for all models with pulsation frequencies, extending the work of (Fitch, 1981), and testing the published scaling relations between $\log Q$ and $\log T_{eff}$. The pulsation constant is expected to be approximately constant for models with similar structure, and Fitch (1981) found that the value of $\log Q$ was essentially independent of temperature for the radial modes up to $n = 7$. However, the coolest model in his grid had a temperature of about $\log T_{eff} \approx 3.8$. The model grid calculated by Lovekin & Guzik extend to temperatures as low as $\log T_{eff} \approx 3.7$. As a result, they found an increase in Q for models with effective temperature less than $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$.

At temperatures higher than $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$, the scaling relations published by Fitch (1981) work well for overshoot parameter $f_{ov} < 0.06$. Above this overshoot, the predicted $\log Q$ values are as much as 0.3 dex higher than expected at all temperatures. This is not surprising, as increased overshoot increases the pulsation frequencies, yet Fitch’s scaling relations for radial modes depend only on the pulsation period. Fitch’s scaling relations are thus missing an important parameter, especially at $\log T_{eff} < 3.83$.

At temperatures below the $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$ breakpoint, the deviation from the expected constant $\log Q$ was most pronounced in the radial fundamental mode. All of the first 7 harmonics showed a significant change in slope at around $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$, as shown in Figure 3. All 7 harmonics can be fit with a piecewise linear function with four free parameters: the break point T_b , the slope for $T < T_b$ (m_{low}), the slope for $T > T_b$ (m_{high}), and the intercept of the linear fit above T_b . Since m_{high} is generally close to zero, the intercept corresponds to the average $\log Q$ at high temperatures. In all fits, the break point T_b was found to be at $\log T_{eff} \approx 3.83$. The slope m_{low} is largest for the radial fundamental mode, and the sign of m_{low} changes for harmonics higher than $n = 3$.

The detailed behaviour of the piecewise fit depends on both the rotation and overshoot of the sample. In particular, the slope of the fit below $\log T = 3.83$ gets smaller as the amount of overshooting in the model increases. Further investigation revealed that the breakpoint in the piecewise function corresponds to the temperature at which the surface convection zone starts to increase. Models with more overshoot below the surface convection zone have slightly larger Q values, leading to the behaviour seen in Figure 3.

They also found that the variation in the slope (m_{low}) can be fit with a linear function for all 7 harmonics. For the radial fundamental mode, the relation is given by

$$m_{low} = (12 \pm 2)f_{ov} - (2.8 \pm 0.1) \quad (5)$$

averaged over all rotation rates. In principle, this could be used to determine the average overshoot parameter f_{ov} of a sample of stars given sufficiently accurate determination of $\log Q$ over a range of temperatures. Lovekin & Guzik (2017) also found that the intercept of the fit above $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$ is related to the amount of rotation in the stellar models. Again, given the values of $\log Q$ for observed stars with $\log T_{eff} > 3.83$, this could be used to constrain the average rotation rate of a sample of stars.

The initial calculations were done using only solar metallicity models. Work is ongoing to extend the model grid to both higher and lower metallicities to see if the same behaviour appears. The lowest metallicity models in the new grid ($Z = 0.001$) are slightly hotter than the previous grid, and new behaviour is seen at temperatures hotter than $\log T = 3.95$. Above this temperature, the Q values again increase slightly. The origin of this behaviour is not yet understood (Dornan & Lovekin, in prep).

In principle, the method described in Lovekin & Guzik (2017) could be used to constrain the overshoot of a sample of radial pulsators, at least in a statistical sense. To test this, Lovekin & Guzik (2017) looked at a sample of 22 High Amplitude δ Scuti stars (HADS) taken from the AAVSO database. These 22 stars were flagged in the database as radial pulsators, and the highest amplitude mode was assumed to correspond to the radial fundamental mode. Effective temperatures were estimated based on the observed B-V, and all stars were assumed to have the same mean density. When plotted in a $\log Q$ vs $\log T_{eff}$ diagram, the stars followed the same piecewise linear function found in the theoretical models, although with a large amount of scatter. A fit to the slope below $\log T_{eff} = 3.83$ found that $m_Q = -2.7 \pm 1.2$, which corresponds to an overshoot of $f_{ov} = 0.008_{0.008}^{+0.4}$. Although many of these assumptions are likely incorrect, this work provides a proof-of-concept that the method could be applied to more accurate observations of real stars to determine the convective overshoot parameter.

4 g-mode pulsators

The g-mode pulsators are predicted to show regular patterns in the period spacing (Tassoul, 1980), which can be used to constrain the composition gradient near the core (Miglio *et al.*, 2008). This in turns means that the period spacing patterns are affected by both rotation and convective core overshoot (Van Reeth *et al.*, 2015a,b; Lovekin & Guzik, 2017; Ouazzani *et al.*, 2017). In rotating models, frequency splitting leads to distinct sequences for prograde, retrograde and zonal modes. Models show that retrograde modes have positive slopes, while prograde and zonal modes have negative slopes, and the magnitude of the slope increases as rotation is increased. Rotation also decreases the average period spacing for the prograde and zonal modes (Ouazzani *et al.*, 2017). Based on the slope of the period spacings, it is possible identify the azimuthal wave number m and the rotation rate of the star.

In more evolved models, the chemical gradient at the convective core boundary leads to the development of periodic dips in the period spacings, and the position and size of the dips is determined by the position and size of the convective boundary (Miglio *et al.*, 2008). As the core hydrogen fraction decreases, the dips in the period spacing become deeper

Figure 4: The period spacing pattern for zonal modes at several different overshoot parameters. These models were calculated using the exponential overshoot prescription given by Equation 2. As the amount of overshooting increases, the dips become smaller, disappearing completely about $f_{ov} = 0.6$.

and closer together in models with no convective overshoot. Since convective overshoot changes the position of the convective boundary and the shape of the chemical gradient, the dips can be used to constrain the convective overshoot in a particular star. As the amount of overshoot increases, the dips become smaller, disappearing completely in models with the highest overshoot, as shown in Figure 4.

These frequency patterns have now been detected in a number of stars, for both prograde and retrograde modes (Van Reeth *et al.*, 2015b, 2016). Once the period spacing has been determined, it can easily be compared to a grid of theoretical period spacings and minimizing the residuals to determine the best fitting properties, as shown in Figure 5. Although the azimuthal number can be determined, this fitting process does not necessarily give complete mode identification. For the fits shown in Figure 5, Van Reeth *et al.* (2016) assumed $(\ell, m) = (1, 1)$, but were able to obtain good results by assuming $(\ell, m) = (2, 1)$ or $(2, 2)$ as well.

Although the process is more challenging for observed period spacings in real stars, (Van Reeth *et al.*, 2016) have been able to place constraints on the rotation rate of about 40 γ Doradus stars using this technique. The process is easiest for stars which have multiple period sequences (prograde, retrograde, and zonal), and the most rapidly rotating stars are still hard to fit. Van Reeth *et al.* (2016) excluded 6 stars that are rapidly rotating and show only retrograde modes. The resulting rotation rates range from $0.07 d^{-1}$ to $2.25 d^{-1}$. The analysis technique used to determine the rotation rates artificially removes the dips to simplify the modelling, which also removes any information about the convective overshoot. However, it should be possible to adapt the method to constrain overshoot as well. Perhaps the biggest limitation of the method is that it is very difficult to automate the process, and the period spacings must be disentangled from the period spectrum by hand.

This technique is still in its infancy, but it has the potential to greatly improve our understanding of convective overshoot. By comparing theoretical models to simulated data, Pedersen *et al.* (2018) showed that it should be possible to use the detailed shape of the dips in the period spacing to dis-

Figure 5: Top: A comparison of theoretical period spacings (squares) compared with simulated data (black dots and grey squares) with the dips excluded. The fit was based only on the black dots. Bottom: The residuals of the fit. Figure from Van Reeth *et al.* (2016).

tinguish between step and exponential overshoot, as well as constrain the extent of the convective overshoot region. At this conference, we saw this done for the first time for a star with a 4-year *Kepler* light curve (Michielson *et al.*, this volume). These preliminary results favour the use of exponential overshoot given in Equation 2 over the step overshoot.

5 Conclusions

Currently, convective overshoot is still constrained on a star-by-star basis, limiting the number of stars with known overshoot parameters. However, great progress has been made. For β Cephei stars, mode identification is essential for ensuring accuracy of the fit. Only a handful of stars have been fit this way, with core overshoot parameters ranging from $\alpha_{ov} = 0.1 - 0.44$. To date, all of these stars have been modelled with step overshoot, although the exponential overshoot seems to be favoured, at least in γ Doradus stars.

In the δ Scuti stars, the rich pulsation spectrum makes individual modelling like in the β Cephei stars impractical. The δ Scuti stars have too many frequencies to fit individual modes effectively, and yet there does not seem to be a convenient pattern to the detected modes as has been done for the γ Doradus stars. The pulsation frequencies in the δ Scuti stars are generally of a low order, and so are not expected to obey the asymptotic frequency relations put forward by Tassoul (1980). There is some indication that δ Scuti stars do show some regularity to their frequencies, and echelle diagrams have been made for some stars (for example García Hernández *et al.*, 2013; Paparó *et al.*, 2016). For models of known large frequency separation $\delta\nu$, Lovekin & Guzik (2017) found that the large frequency separation increased with both rotation and convective overshoot. At the present time, there does not seem to be a practical way to disentangle the two effects, so it is not clear that this can be used to determine the convective overshoot parameter in individual δ Scuti stars. The $\log Q$ technique described here and in Lovekin & Guzik (2017) may make it possible to measure the convective overshoot of a sample of δ Scuti stars, but the observational precision required makes this difficult to achieve in practice.

The greatest progress has been made on the SPB and γ Do-

radus stars, as described in Section 4. The period spacings in these stars form regular patterns that have been used to constrain convective overshoot and rotation, as well as perform limited mode identification. This technique does not require spectroscopic follow up, and can be done on relatively faint stars. The success in this area is especially important given the γ Doradus stars location at the transition between convective and radiative cores. In the near future, these stars will be used to determine the best fitting form of the overshoot region, and overshoot parameters will be determined for a number of stars, allowing us to begin to understand how overshoot varies with mass and age. Again, the γ Doradus stars are fortuitously located, as they span the $2 M_{\odot}$ point where it has been suggested the overshoot parameter stabilizes (Claret & Torres, 2016). Although we have much work to do to fully understand convective overshoot, promising techniques exist, and we can expect to see significant progress in the next few years.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported in part by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. NSF PHY-1125915. This work was supported in part by NASA ATP grant 12-ATP12-0130 and in part by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC). The authors are grateful to the Kavli Institute at UCSB and the organizers of the Massive Star program for providing the opportunity to visit. This research has made use of NASA’s Astrophysics Data System, the International Variable Star Index (VSX) database, operated at AAVSO, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA, and the SIMBAD database, operated at CDS, Strasbourg, France. Computational facilities are provided by ACENET, and Compute Canada (www.computeCanada.ca). ACENET is funded by the Canada Foundation for Innovation (CFI), the Atlantic Canada Opportunities Agency (ACOA), and the provinces of Newfoundland and Labrador, Nova Scotia, and New Brunswick.

References

- Aerts, C., Thoul, A., Daszyńska, J., Scuflaire, R., Waelkens, C., *et al.* 2003, *Science*, 300, 1926.
- Aerts, C., Waelkens, C., Daszyńska-Daszkiewicz, J., Dupret, M. A., Thoul, A., *et al.* 2004, *A&A*, 415, 241.
- Ausseloos, M., Scuflaire, R., Thoul, A., & Aerts, C. 2004, *MNRAS*, 355, 352.
- Auvergne, M., Bodin, P., Boissard, L., Buey, J. T., Chaintreuil, S., *et al.* 2009, *A&A*, 506, 411.
- Balona, L. A. 2016, *MNRAS*, 459, 1097.
- Briquet, M., Lefever, K., Uytterhoeven, K., & Aerts, C. 2005, *MNRAS*, 362, 619.
- Briquet, M., Morel, T., Thoul, A., Scuflaire, R., Miglio, A., *et al.* 2007, *MNRAS*, 381, 1482.
- Claret, A. & Torres, G. 2016, *A&A*, 592, A15.
- Demarque, P., Woo, J.-H., Kim, Y.-C., & Yi, S. K. 2004, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 155, 667.
- Desmet, M., Briquet, M., Thoul, A., Zima, W., De Cat, P., *et al.* 2009, *MNRAS*, 396, 1460.
- Deupree, R. G. 1990, *ApJ*, 357, 175.
- Deupree, R. G. 1995, *ApJ*, 439, 357.
- Dupret, M. A., Grigahcène, A., Garrido, R., Gabriel, M., & Scuflaire, R. 2005, *A&A*, 435, 927.
- Eggenberger, P., Miglio, A., Montalbán, J., Moreira, O., Noels, A., *et al.* 2010, *A&A*, 509, A72.
- Fitch, W. S. 1981, *ApJ*, 249, 218.
- García Hernández, A., Moya, A., Michel, E., Suárez, J. C., Poretti, E., *et al.* 2013, *A&A*, 559, A63.

- Guzik, J. A., Kaye, A. B., Bradley, P. A., Cox, A. N., & Neuforge, C. 2000, *ApJ*, 542, L57.
- Handler, G., Jerzykiewicz, M., Rodríguez, E., Uytterhoeven, K., Amado, P. J., *et al.* 2006, *MNRAS*, 365, 327.
- Handler, G., Shobbrook, R. R., & Mokgwetsi, T. 2005, *MNRAS*, 362, 612.
- Herwig, F. 2000, *A&A*, 360, 952.
- Koch, D. G., Borucki, W. J., Basri, G., Batalha, N. M., Brown, T. M., *et al.* 2010, *ApJ*, 713, L79.
- Lee, Y.-H., Kim, S. S., Shin, J., Lee, J., & Jin, H. 2008, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of Japan*, 60, 551.
- Lovekin, C. C. & Goupil, M. J. 2010, *A&A*, 515, A58.
- Lovekin, C. C. & Guzik, J. A. 2017, *ApJ*, 849, 38.
- Mazumdar, A., Briquet, M., Desmet, M., & Aerts, C. 2006, *A&A*, 459, 589.
- Miglio, A., Montalbán, J., Noels, A., & Eggenberger, P. 2008, *MNRAS*, 386, 1487.
- Neiner, C., Mathis, S., Saio, H., Lovekin, C., Eggenberger, P., *et al.* 2012, *A&A*, 539, A90.
- Ouazzani, R.-M., Salmon, S. J. A. J., Antoci, V., Bedding, T. R., Murphy, S. J., *et al.* 2017, *MNRAS*, 465, 2294.
- Paparo, M., Benkó, J. M., Hareter, M., & Guzik, J. A. 2016, *ApJ*, 822, 100.
- Paxton, B., Bildsten, L., Dotter, A., Herwig, F., Lesaffre, P., *et al.* 2011, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 192, 3.
- Paxton, B., Cantiello, M., Arras, P., Bildsten, L., Brown, E. F., *et al.* 2013, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 208, 4.
- Paxton, B., Marchant, P., Schwab, J., Bauer, E. B., Bildsten, L., *et al.* 2015, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 220, 15.
- Paxton, B., Schwab, J., Bauer, E. B., Bildsten, L., Blinnikov, S., *et al.* 2018, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 234, 34.
- Pedersen, M. G., Aerts, C., Pápics, P. I., & Rogers, T. M. 2018, *A&A*, 614, A128.
- Ricker, G. R., Winn, J. N., Vanderspek, R., Latham, D. W., Bakos, G. Á., *et al.* 2015, *Journal of Astronomical Telescopes, Instruments, and Systems*, 1, 014003.
- Schwarzschild, M. 1958, *Structure and evolution of the stars*.
- Tassoul, M. 1980, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 43, 469.
- Townsend, R. H. D. & Teitler, S. A. 2013, *MNRAS*, 435, 3406.
- Van Reeth, T., Tkachenko, A., & Aerts, C. 2016, *A&A*, 593, A120.
- Van Reeth, T., Tkachenko, A., Aerts, C., Pápics, P. I., Degroote, P., *et al.* 2015a, *A&A*, 574, A17.
- Van Reeth, T., Tkachenko, A., Aerts, C., Pápics, P. I., Triana, S. A., *et al.* 2015b, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 218, 27.
- Walker, G., Matthews, J., Kuschnig, R., Johnson, R., Rucinski, S., *et al.* 2003, *Publications of the Astronomical Society of the Pacific*, 115, 1023.